

ORGANIZATION OF LECTURES, PRACTICAL TRAINING AND INDEPENDENT WORK IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663134>

Abstract. In the article, the content and essence of students' innovations in the creation of graphic exercises and tasks through the lecture, practical training and independent work on the subject of "Fuel and Lubricants" is described in detail.

Key words: Practical training, lectures, student's independent work, quantitative criteria.

Experiential training is a form of training that allows the teacher to engage in active communication with students and to implement theoretical knowledge and creative skills in practical activities.

Practice training classes can be divided into two types. These are lecture and non-lecture subjects.

Practical training classes are held in strict accordance with subject programs and work programs, as well as calendar thematic plans, and a list of necessary literature and equipment for conducting practical training is provided.

Experiential training is used to achieve the following goals:

- arrangement of theoretical material;
- formation of skills;
- control of knowledge.

There are great opportunities to use new pedagogical technologies or interactive methods in practice training classes. The teacher enters the class and conducts organizational work. The topic of the lesson is announced and written on the board. The main content of the previous topic is briefly described and a plan of the new topic is given. In the lecture, the main conclusions of the materials are explained, and the lecture is connected with the practical training. Experimental training can be conducted in different ways depending on the characteristics of the subject and even the topics.

In addition to practice tests, questions and answers, discussions are organized in practical training classes, students who actively participate are encouraged and given points. The teacher conducting the science lecture must regularly monitor the high-quality conduct of the experimental training classes according to the strict program, the timely evaluation of the students' knowledge.

It is estimated that it will take a lot of time to transfer the experience to classes. Also, it was noted that the experimental materials are not received uniformly by the students, as a result, some of the students (sometimes the majority) cannot understand the presented material, they only mechanically record the words.

There are many benefits of experience classes. Experience allows you to master the core of the topics. It is also conducted in small groups. It is necessary to prepare and deliver all educational materials from practical training to students, and to have pedagogical skills that allow students to accept these materials. Along with explaining the new topic, he has to

connect the previous topic and bring it to the students' memory. In the course of fuels and lubricants, experimental materials are collected and summarized from various sources.

However, in the Fuels and Lubricants module, there are practical exercises that students must learn that cannot be done in the classroom. In such cases, the teacher should properly process the material and present it in a form that is convenient for understanding and mastering, paying attention to the explanation of very difficult aspects.

Lectures play an important role in passing practical lessons.

Lectures are a very economical way to get the basics of knowledge, focus on the learning material in a summarized way. In an oral presentation, many students understand the material more easily and get the main idea, the logic of the argumentation, the structure of the educational material becomes clearer. Thus, in all of the above-mentioned cases, the lecture is really a necessary form in the acquisition and transfer of knowledge of the academic subject.

In the literature, lecture is considered as a traditional form of education and some disadvantages are mentioned: low level of student acquisition, student engagement, low feedback, lack of student interest.

First of all, the student should understand and read the new educational material presented by the teacher, he should not only listen to the speaker, but also actively participate in the lecture and answer questions based on his interest. If the student can understand the speaker's point of view, the learning material is mastered. After carefully following the information transmitted by the teacher, the development of the speaker's thoughts, if he can connect the new information with the previously known information and understand what he heard, a certain mental activity will be awakened in the student. The comprehension phase is critical to the mastery process.

The main purpose of the lecture is to increase the intellectual power of students, to create a movement of thinking that follows the teacher's thoughts, to achieve cooperative thinking and reaction.

In our opinion, when conducting a lecture course on the science of fuels and lubricants, the educational process is presented with visual material and information that demonstrates some theoretical rules.

As a reinforcement of the learning process, the Fuels and Lubricants classes use problem situations to give students a thorough understanding of the subject. The process of completing problem exercises puts the student in a new position of knowledge. It involves methods and techniques previously unknown to students. allows conducting lecture classes using interactive teaching methods. Experimental training is considered a form of education that ensures the student's mastery and strengthening of the subject.

Reinforces and expands the knowledge gained during the lecture. The student performs the assigned tasks independently based on the acquired knowledge. Experimental training in the science of fuels and lubricants is conducted in small groups. During the organization of practical training, pre-prepared handouts, methodical instructions are distributed to each student, and the theoretical part is shown.

This is done with the help of handouts: continuous review of the presentation material necessary for the completion of individual tasks, focused on strengthening knowledge.

The most effective means of developing and strengthening creative activity is the independent work of the student, which is the basis for improving the quality of training of specialists.

It was developed on the basis of the decision No. 311 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 16, 2021 "On approval of state educational standards of higher education" and the "Instructions on the organization and control of independent work of students" of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. The student's independent work is an integral part of the educational work specified in the curriculum for mastering a particular subject.

It is necessary to increase the role of their independent work, taking into account the fact that the knowledge and skills acquired independently by students of science programs become more complicated and expanded from course to course. Then the student not only completes the tasks set by the teacher, but also tries to independently select and master the additional knowledge that he considers necessary for his professional activity, depending on his needs, interests and abilities. out of sight.

If necessary, they get advice from the teacher. An abstract on the subject is prepared on the computer and handed over to the science teacher. The science teacher evaluates the student according to the content of the assigned task, the richness of the obtained information and other characteristics.

The tasks of the student's independent work are as follows:

- effective use of information sources and addresses in the performance of independent work;
- to work with electronic educational literature and data bank while performing independent work, to find the most convenient solution to given assignments and tasks;
- preparation of independent work results for examination and processing on the basis of expert opinion;
- planned and creative approach to independent work;
- justification and defense of a solution, project or idea developed in independent work in a team of experts.

The main goal of the student's independent work is to form and develop the knowledge and skills necessary for students to independently perform the given independent work under the guidance and control of the teacher.

To combine and organize one's own capabilities to solve the assigned tasks;

- to control his own activities and evaluate accordingly, to monitor his own further actions and to carry out self-evaluation.

Learning outcomes may include learning and applying a known method or technique to a given task, or detailed instruction or instruction on a work procedure.

It is necessary for the student to be introduced to the form and type of control: written essay, report, abstract, etc., oral presentation, answering questions, etc., as well as qualitative and quantitative criteria for evaluating each educational task. In addition, it is necessary for a student to use modern computer and information technologies to search, find, collect, and process information while doing independent work.

Monitoring and evaluation of students' independent work is carried out on the basis of the counseling schedule established in the department and approved by the head of the department.

In accordance with the time allotted for student independent work in the curriculum, organizational forms of independent work, assignment options are developed and approved at the department meeting in relevant departments. For students to do independent work,

educational and methodological instructions and recommendations are developed and distributed to students as handouts.

The form and size of tasks given for independent work, the degree of difficulty should vary from simple to complex. That is, the level of students' independence in completing tasks should gradually increase.

In addition, it is important to develop educational materials that provide independent learning and conduct experiments.

When performing independent work, it is necessary to take into account the volume of educational materials and the coverage of the complex system of questions and tasks.

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